

Data-Driven Visibility: Nodal Voltage Estimation from Limited Substation Data

Agnia Dewi Larasati, Anurag Mohapatra, Thomas Hamacher
 Technical University of Munich, Germany
 {agn.larasati, anurag.mohapatra, thomas.hamacher}@tum.de

Abstract—Germany mandates a nationwide smart-meter deployment by 2032. However, the regulations do not require real-time data transfer, and the current national penetration is only about 3% of households. Consequently, Distribution System Operators (DSOs) lack the live visibility needed to control voltages in increasingly active distribution grids with high shares of renewable generation and sector-coupled loads. This paper presents a data-driven framework that estimates live voltage states across all grid nodes using “available but delayed” historical smart meter data, together with “aggregated but live” transformer measurements. A Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network with feature engineering is applied to predict instantaneous voltage states with high accuracy across a variety of test scenarios on a benchmark rural distribution grid with realistic measurement noise. The proposed predictor matches, and in some cases exceeds, the performance of multilayer-perceptron-based approaches across all test cases. The results demonstrate the ability of recurrent neural networks to learn deep temporal embeddings that effectively disaggregate transformer measurements and map them to nodal voltages.

Index Terms—distribution system state estimation, low-voltage grids, Long Short-Term Memory, smart meter data, tariff application case.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Federal Republic of Germany has long supported Renewable Energy Systems (RES), introducing one of the earliest feed-in tariffs in 1991. The European Union later reinforced this transition through the Renewable Energy Directive, targeting at least 42.5% RES by 2030. As renewable penetration increases, detailed and timely energy data become essential for grid optimization and the integration of distributed energy resources (DER). To support this, the EU introduced intelligent metering systems (iMSys) in Directives 2009/72/EC and 2009/73/EC [1]. Germany adopted these requirements through the Messstellenbetriebsgesetz (MsbG) in 2016 [2], mandating the installation of iMSys for high-consumption customers and medium-scale generators by 2032. However, strict certification requirements, bundled use cases, and legal rulings in 2021–2022 have significantly slowed the rollout [3].

Each metering point in Germany is assigned a Tariff Application Case (TAF) that defines its data reporting scheme [4]. The commonly deployed TAF 1 and TAF 7 provide only energy readings, while TAF 10 adds voltage magnitude and phase angle. TAF 14 increases reporting frequency but does not include voltage data. TAF 10 and TAF 14 are rarely activated in residential settings, rendering real-time voltage reporting unavailable. Importantly, not all metering points are

required to have a communication channel or a Smart Meter Gateway (SMGW), meaning real-time data transfer is unavailable by default. Installing an SMGW requires individual on-site deployment and incurs additional cost, which has slowed the nationwide rollout: voluntary installations remain below 3% as of March 2025 [5]. Consequently, real-time voltage observability in low-voltage grids remains severely limited.

Given this lack of detailed voltage information, data-driven techniques have gained traction for Distribution System State Estimation (DSSE), supporting tasks such as pseudo-measurement generation and voltage estimation [6]. In [7], voltage magnitude and active power injection are estimated using real substation measurements together with exogenous features (temperature, irradiance, historical profiles), achieving a typical RMSE below 0.2% on the Aspern Smart City Research Testbed. An LSTM-based DSSE in [8] provides more accurate and faster voltage estimates than a conventional weighted least squares (WLS) estimator on the IEEE 34-bus system. Similarly, [9] demonstrates that a Neural Network model-free voltage calculation methodology utilizing only historical active and reactive power from low-voltage customers achieves a voltage RMSE of below 1.6 V on a 100% photovoltaics (PV) penetration, indicating that reliable voltage estimation is feasible without detailed electrical network models. The methodology also considered an integrated MV-LV network with over 3,400 customers to account for upstream voltage fluctuations, all simulated on a realistic network using real consumption data.

MLP-based model-free voltage methods learn the instantaneous mapping between (P, Q) and bus voltages without requiring grid models and compute voltages very quickly [9]. However, their topology-agnostic design limits their ability to generalize under switching events or unseen grid configurations, and their phase-angle accuracy remains below classical WLS [10]. Meanwhile, LSTM-based DSSE methods exploit temporal dependencies [8], allowing them to capture system dynamics, infer hidden states, and also maintain high accuracy under sparse measurements. LSTMs have shown lower RMSE than WLS in hybrid AC/DC networks and can be compressed via weight pruning while preserving performance, making them effective for DSSE under varying operating conditions.

To address the limited voltage observability in German LV grids, this paper proposes a data-driven voltage state estimation framework that uses only real-time active and reactive power measurements from substations during operation, which are readily available data to DSOs. The complete schematic of

Fig. 1. a) Schematic of the proposed data-driven low-voltage state estimation framework. b) Used SimBench topology with marked scenario 1 and 2 for Subsection III-E.

the proposed approach is shown in Fig. 1a. The model is trained offline using historical smart-meter and substation data, allowing it to learn typical consumption patterns and voltage behavior despite the limited and uneven deployment of voltage-capable meters in Germany. The proposed approach employs sequence-to-sequence (seq2seq) and sequence-to-one (seq2one) LSTM architectures with temporal features to capture diurnal and periodic grid behavior. By jointly estimating voltage magnitude and phase angle, the model leverages their inherent coupling to produce consistent voltage profiles. The method is evaluated on the SimBench LV benchmark with different grid stiffness levels and temporal resolutions, demonstrating stable and accurate performance. The results show that reliable voltage estimation is achievable using only non-voltage measurements, offering TAF 10- and TAF 14-equivalent functionality without requiring additional sensor infrastructure. This improves observability in a cost-efficient and operationally feasible manner.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section II provides a brief description of the proposed methodology, Section III presents the results and discussion, and Section IV concludes the paper.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Problem Formulation

Conventional low-voltage monitoring systems lack direct measurements of voltage magnitude and angle under the standard tariff application cases TAF 1 and TAF 7. The task is thus formulated as a data-driven DSSE problem in which the objective is to reconstruct the full voltage state vector (V_{mag}, V_{θ}) at all network nodes using historical aggregated substation active and reactive power measurements (P, Q), historical smart meter readings, and temporal features. Unlike traditional model-based DSSE approaches [8], [11] that require detailed grid topology and sufficient measurement redundancy, the method estimates voltage states directly from limited historical data. The problem is treated as a multivariate sequence regression task in which sequences of (P, Q) and time features are mapped to nodal voltage states. Both sequence-to-one and sequence-to-sequence LSTM architectures are evaluated to examine the influence of temporal context length on estimation performance.

B. Data Source and Preprocessing

The experiment aims to estimate voltage magnitude (V_{mag}) and angle (V_{θ}) across all buses of an LV grid using only

substation active and reactive power measurements (P, Q). The test system is based on the SimBench “1-LV-rural2-0-sw” scenario [12], which represents a rural radial network with 96 buses, one 250 kVA transformer, and eight PV systems. Power flow data for 2016 at 15-minute resolution are generated in Python using `pandapower` [13].

A virtual slack bus is connected to bus 62 through a Thevenin impedance, modeling the upstream grid with $S_{SC} = 5$ MVA and $R/X = 7$, while a weaker grid is simulated with $S_{SC} = 1.75$ MVA. Two temporal resolutions are evaluated: (1) a 15-minute case reflecting TAF 10, and (2) a 5-second case resembling TAF 14, obtained by Piecewise Cubic Hermite Interpolating Polynomial (PCHIP) upsampling. Gaussian noise truncated to $\pm 2\sigma$ (1% of signal amplitude, per MID Class B accuracy [14]) is added to P and Q to emulate sensor uncertainty and enhance robustness.

The final model utilizes substation-level P and Q (with optional time features) as inputs and predicts V_{mag} and V_{θ} for all 95 residential buses. The LV slack bus distributes power, and a grid-equivalent bus represents the upstream network. The grid topology is shown in Fig. 1b.

TABLE I
MODEL HYPERPARAMETERS FOR MLP AND LSTM

Parameter	MLP	LSTM
Architecture	1 hidden layer	4 layers
Units	$5n_{out}$	192
Activation	\tanh	\tanh
Optimizer	Adam	Adam
Loss function	RMSE	RMSE
Learning rate	2×10^{-4}	2×10^{-4}
Batch size	112	112
Training epochs	100	100, 25

C. Model Architecture

LSTM networks are used as the primary architecture due to their ability to capture temporal dependencies in sequential power system data. This enables learning the dynamic relationship between substation measurements and voltage states. Two LSTM configurations are evaluated in this work: a seq2seq and a seq2one model. The seq2seq architecture, implemented as stacked LSTMs that output a full prediction sequence, captures richer temporal structure and strengthens consecutive sequence prediction [16]. It has shown robust performance across both high and low-resolution datasets in [15] and can flexibly map input sequences of arbitrary length to multi-step outputs. The

Fig. 2. Testing strategy for the state estimator.

seq2one model, which predicts only the final state of the window, is considerably lighter, typically reducing trainable parameters by 30 to 60% and training substantially faster while maintaining strong accuracy for short-horizon estimation. Evaluating both architectures enables a clear comparison between the robustness and computational efficiency for real-world DSSE applications.

Model training and inference were accelerated by utilizing a high-performance computing cluster at the Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) using the NVIDIA Ampere A100 GPUs. Table I summarizes the hyperparameters used for the model searched with Bayesian Optimization. To benchmark performance, a feedforward multilayer perceptron (MLP) model is trained using the same input features as the LSTM model before proceeding with the analysis. The hyperparameters for MLP were chosen based on the models documented by [7]. While comparing LSTM and MLP, both are trained with 100 epochs to have a fair comparison between recurrent and non-recurrent architectures. The 15-minute resolution data comprises one year of SimBench historical data, while the high-resolution one considers only two weeks of data, divided into 70% training, 15% validating, and 15% testing data.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The testing strategy is illustrated in Fig. 2. First, both LSTM and MLP models are evaluated to establish a performance benchmark. In *Analysis 1*, the seq2seq and seq2one architectures are compared to determine the preferred structure for subsequent experiments. *Analysis 2* examines the effect of including temporal features as auxiliary inputs. In *Analysis 3*, different output configurations are tested to assess whether predicting voltage magnitude alone or jointly with angle yields better performance. Finally, *Analysis 4* performs hyperparameter optimization across three parameters: temporal resolution, lookback horizon, and spatial scope, to identify the optimal model configuration.

A. LSTM vs. MLP

To provide a fair comparison and establish a benchmark, this work evaluates both MLP and LSTM models on the proposed dataset. The first model tested is a seq2seq stacked LSTM with inputs of (P, Q) at the substation and outputs

Fig. 3. LSTM vs. MLP, Voltage a) Magnitude, and b) Angle for Bus 39.

of (V_{mag}, V_{θ}) . The model is trained and tested on a typical grid with a 24-hour lookback, using data with a 15-minute resolution and an RMSE loss function. This LSTM model is compared to the MLP model described in subsection II-C. Table II shows the complete results of the benchmark tests, and Fig. 3 compares predicted and measured measurements at the worst predicted bus. The training times are approximately 3 minutes for the MLP model and 75 minutes for the seq2seq LSTM with 100 epochs. MLP-based approaches are effective due to their topology-agnostic design and fast inference [9]. The two models perform comparably overall, with the LSTM showing a slight advantage. Given this, the LSTM is used for the subsequent analyses (Analyses 1–4), while the MLP is retained in Analysis 3 to allow direct comparison to the voltage-magnitude estimation setup considered in [9].

B. Analysis 1: Seq2one and Seq2seq Comparison

Now that a baseline has been established showing that the LSTM performs comparably to the MLP, the next design choice concerns the comparison between seq2seq and seq2one architectures. From the hyperparameter search, 25 training epochs were found to be sufficient for the LSTM model, as validation performance stagnated beyond this point; all subsequent experiments therefore use 25 epochs. The first analysis evaluates the seq2seq and seq2one LSTM configurations, with the results of Analyses 1 to 3 summarized in Table II.

The seq2seq framework more effectively captures temporal dependencies and multi-step structure across the input window, enabling it to model the joint evolution of V_{mag} , V_{θ} , P , and Q with greater fidelity. However, this enhanced capability comes at the cost of approximately 30–60% more trainable parameters. This increased computational burden motivates the use of the lighter seq2one configuration for high-resolution data, where memory efficiency becomes critical.

C. Analysis 2: Effect of Time Features

Electrical demand and PV generation exhibit strong daily, weekly, and seasonal cycles. Adding time features helps the model recognize these periodic patterns without relying solely on sequence memory, reducing the LSTM’s learning burden and improving generalization. Four temporal features are introduced: sine and cosine of the hour, and of the day-of-the-week. Although the baseline errors are already small, adding time

TABLE II
STATE ESTIMATION RESULTS FOR ANALYSIS 1-3. ALL VALUES ARE $\times 10^{-4}$. THE MAE IS SHOWN FOR THE WORST PERFORMING BUS.

Category	Model	Magnitude (p.u.)		Angle ($^{\circ}$)	
		RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE
Benchmark*	MLP	3.5	4.9	64	90
	LSTM	2.8	3.8	54	72
#1: Seq2Seq vs Seq2One	LSTM_Seq2Seq	2.9	4.1	55	72
	LSTM_Seq2One	13.0	13.0	360	340
#2: Time or not	VMVA_Seq2Seq	2.7	3.4	54	69
#3: Only Magnitude	LSTM_Seq2Seq_time	2.7	3.5	—	—
	MLP_time	3.2	4.6	—	—

*These models are trained with 100 epochs. The highlighted model is chosen as the baseline for further analyses.

features further reduces them. The training–validation gap also decreases, indicating more stable learning of periodic behavior. Given these benefits, the temporal features are retained for all subsequent analyses.

D. Analysis 3: Magnitude-Only Ablation

In this analysis, voltage angle is removed from the prediction targets to assess whether its inclusion meaningfully improves estimation performance. Prior work [7], [11] often focused on voltage magnitude alone, partly because LV grids rarely feature widespread phasor measurements. However, under TAF 10, voltage angle becomes available, and many LV and MV networks do not satisfy the simplifying assumption $R \gg X$; in such cases, active and reactive power flows are more strongly coupled with both V_{mag} and V_{θ} .

The magnitude-only model yields a small improvement in global RMSE but remains close to the joint model. An MLP trained on magnitude with time features is also evaluated, and the LSTM achieves comparable performance to the MLP used in [9], despite operating under more limited measurement availability. Given the physical coupling in AC power flow and the availability of angle under TAF 10, the joint estimation of magnitude and angle is retained. This combined model provides the most consistent performance across analyses and is selected as the baseline, highlighted in blue in Tab. II.

TABLE III
VOLTAGE ESTIMATION RESULTS FOR ANALYSIS 4. ALL VALUES ARE $\times 10^{-4}$. THE MAE IS SHOWN FOR THE WORST PERFORMING BUS.

Category	Model / Scenario	Magnitude (p.u.)		Angle ($^{\circ}$)	
		RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE
All-bus Analysis					
5-s Resolution	Lookback 5 min	4.3	6.4	79	114
	Lookback 30 min	4.5	6.6	80	110
15-min Resolution	Lookback 12 h	2.8	3.5	54	69
	Baseline: Lookback 24 h	2.7	3.4	54	69
	Lookback 48 h	2.8	3.7	56	69
Five-bus Analysis					
Endpoints	15 m, 24 h lookback	5.7	4.6	110	84
	5 s, 5 m lookback	9.1	6.9	140	113
	5 s, 30 m lookback	8.4	6.3	130	107
PV & Endpoints	15 m, 24 h lookback	4.1	4.2	79	77
	15 m, Weak Grid	5.1	4.3	31	84
	5 s, 5 m lookback	6.2	6.5	102	104

Fig. 4. Distribution graph of the baseline model (Seq2seq, 24 h lookback, 15-minute resolution).

Fig. 5. Model tested on a weak grid on the worst performing bus in a five-bus analysis (Scenario 2).

Fig. 6. Scatter plots of predicted vs. true voltage magnitude (a), (c) and angle (b), (d) for the worst performing bus under all-bus and five-bus configurations.

E. Analysis 4: Hyperparameter Testing

Using the seq2seq LSTM model with a 24-hour lookback as the baseline (Fig. 4), the following analysis explores whether alternative data resolutions, lookback lengths, and reduced output sizes can achieve similar accuracy with less computational

Fig. 7. Comparison of high resolution five bus analysis at endpoints.

effort. High-resolution 5-second data are first introduced. Because these sequences are much longer, the configuration uses a 30-minute lookback and a seq2one architecture to keep training feasible. The high-resolution dataset also spans a shorter calendar period and shows higher variance, which explains the moderate accuracy reduction in Tab. III. Despite this, performance remains stable, with voltage-magnitude deviations contained within a narrow range.

Different lookback lengths are also tested, showing that 24 hours yields the best performance for 15-minute data, while 5 minutes is optimal for 5-second data, reflecting the difference between the long-term diurnal structure in low-resolution data and the strong short-term autocorrelation in high-resolution data. The seq2one LSTM models completed 25 epochs in about 20–30 minutes, whereas the larger seq2seq LSTM models required roughly 40–60 minutes.

A reduced five-bus estimation task is also evaluated to test whether focusing on a subset of electrically important nodes can improve tractability without sacrificing accuracy. Two configurations, as shown in Fig. 1b, are considered: (i) five endpoint buses, where voltage drops are typically largest, and (ii) three PV buses combined with two weak-performing endpoints representing locations with strong voltage variability. These scenarios reflect realistic situations in which only a few critical nodes are observable.

In both scenarios, the five-bus models maintain, and in some instances slightly improve, the accuracy compared to the full 95-bus estimation, especially when using high-resolution data. Scenario 2 also performs consistently under both typical and weak-grid conditions as shown in Fig. 5. Plots in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 confirm further that reduced-target configurations can achieve reliable performance while lowering computational requirements, providing a 10% faster training time compared to the all-bus LSTM models.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work demonstrates that even without access to online smart meter data, machine learning models like LSTMs can effectively reconstruct near real-time grid states using routinely collected measurements from transformers. This method offers a practical and cost-effective approach for DSOs to enhance voltage observability and control while operating within the constraints of existing infrastructure and regulatory frameworks. Future research should explore the framework's

applicability to rural and suburban grids, which have varied voltage characteristics and higher penetration of PV systems, to evaluate its scalability across different operating conditions. Additionally, combining data-driven techniques, such as LSTM models, with physically informed methods like Physics-Informed Neural Networks or symbolic regression could improve robustness and adaptability by integrating physical principles with data-driven learning.

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